

ppq · react
brand book

The Vision

The project aims for a wide diffusion, exchange and uptake among the Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC) ecosystem, fostering the transference of knowledge and replication.

The interest of this group is tied up to investigate, operate and monetise advances in future-proof cryptography and the influence of quantum technology on security and privacy.

The Mission

PQ-REACT will deliver technical capabilities that enable cryptographic systems to be secure against attacks using quantum or/and classical computers.

Therefore, the project shall assess the requirements of the application sectors that will undertake the migration, replacement and upgrade of their infrastructures.

PQ-REACT will primarily engage with early adopters from the pilots, namely Smart Grid, 5G/B5G, Distributed Ledger product/solution providers, striving for paths towards exploitation and industrial commitment in the longer term.

TARGET AUDIENCE

Target Persona

Male/Female

28-70 years old

Senior researcher, professor or executive member
of RTOs and tech universities

Higher education level (Master's degree or PhD)

Involved in innovation research pertaining to the
fields of encryption and quantum computing

Target Persona

Male/Female

25-40 years old

Tech start-up founder or high-level manager of a SME

High education level (Bachelor's degree and above)

Passionate about technological innovation, strongly involved in the growth plans for the company, looking to bring meaningful change to the world through their work

Target Persona

Male/Female

40-70 years old

High-level manager of a R&D department in a big corporation in the tech field

Higher education level (Master's degree or PhD)

Involved in the strategic decision-making process to foster technological innovation and progress within the company

PERSONALITY

The archetypes

In storytelling, archetypes are used to create an immediate sense of familiarity between the audience and a character. This is also true of your brand story and this is why brand archetypes are an important marketing tool.

These archetypes will help guide the Tone of Voice of PQ-REACT, giving indications on how we should talk about the relevant topics based on the target audience, in order to ensure that all of our communications resonate with them.

The Creator

The creator has a vision and a desire to create an enduring product or experience which realises their vision. They are innovators and non-conformists and are often the first to realise a concept and push the boundaries of creativity and design. They empower others to think creatively and express themselves through the products they produce and the experiences they create.

Desire: Create the perfect product/service

Goal: Innovation

Strategy: Use creativity to solve problems

Brand Message: “Think different”

The Sage

The Sage archetype, called 'senex' (old man in Latin) by Jung, is a seeker of knowledge and wisdom and believes that truth will set you free. They do not look to change the world themselves but prefer to empower others to do so by seeking out valuable information and sharing it. They are often life-long learners and thought leaders and make excellent mentors.

Desire: Find the Truth

Goal: Understanding

Strategy: Seek information and knowledge

Brand Message: "The truth will set you free"

VISUAL TOOLS

typography

Titles

Josefin Sans Bold

abcdefghijklmn
opqrstuvwxyz
1234567890

Download the font family [here](#)

Longer texts

Lato Light

abcdefghijklmn
opqrstuvwxyz
1234567890

Download the font family [here](#)

color guide

primary

#1D3D6B

#FF7FFF

secondary

#873C87

#A2CDFF

#FFA35D

neutrals

#FFFFFF

#4F5056

logo variations

MOCKUPS

Title example

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Title example

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Title example

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